

A Morphological Study of the External Carotid Artery with Reference to Adjacent Anatomical Landmarks in Cadavers

Vipin Kumar¹, Raag Reeti², Abhishek Prasad Sinha³

¹Professor and HOD, Department of Anatomy, Netaji Subhas Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Netaji Subhas Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India

³Professor, Department of Anatomy, R.D. J.M Medical College and Hospital Turki, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India

Received: 25-12-2022 / Revised: 20-01-2023 / Accepted: 08-02-2023

Corresponding author: Dr. Vipin Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of this observational study was to establish the relationship of External Carotid Artery with reference to Adjacent Anatomical landmarks in cadavers.

Methods: The present observational study was done in the Department of Anatomy, Netaji Subhas medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India. 60 hemi-necks obtained from 30 formalin embalmed cadavers (20 male and 10 female) were dissected and the external carotid arteries were traced from the origin to termination.

Results: The ECA took origin at the level of upper border of thyroid cartilage (TC) in 40/60 cases (66.66%). Higher level of origin was noted in the remaining 20 of 60 cases (33.34%). Higher levels of carotid bifurcation were further categorized keeping the TC as anatomical landmark. No lower levels of origin were noted in this study. The anteromedial position of the ECA relative to the ICA at the level of the carotid bifurcation was noted in all the cases.

Conclusion: The exact anatomical knowledge of External Carotid Artery with reference to adjacent anatomical landmarks is helpful for surgeons to plan surgeries and prevent complications during various diagnostic and therapeutic procedures.

Keywords: External Carotid Artery, Anatomical Landmark, Cadaver, Carotid Tubercle.

This is an Open Access article that uses a fund-ing model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The arterial supply of head and neck region is mainly derived from the carotid system of arteries. Additional supply comes from the branches of the subclavian artery, most importantly the vertebral artery. The carotid system of arteries begins as the common carotid artery (CCA), which bifurcates into the external carotid artery (ECA) and the internal carotid artery (ICA). [1] The level of

carotid bifurcation cannot be predicted by any known clinical sign. Most of the literature states that bifurcation of the common carotid artery occurs at the level of the superior border of the thyroid cartilage. [2]

The external carotid artery (ECA) and its branches serve as the major vascular channels of the head and neck region. The ECA arises in the carotid triangle from the

common carotid artery (CCA) along with the internal carotid artery (ICA). The ECA is the main feeding vessel to the tissues of the head and neck region through its 8 branches, namely the superior thyroid artery (STA), ascending pharyngeal artery (APA), lingual artery (LA), facial artery (FA), occipital artery, posterior auricular artery (PAA), superficial temporal artery, and maxillary artery. In addition, the ECAs also play an important role in providing collateral blood supply to the brain through the many connections between the branches of the ECA and cranial branches of the ICA and vertebral arteries. [3] Injuries to the carotid arteries in cases of neck trauma are the cause of inaccessible exsanguinating haemorrhage, requiring emergency surgical intervention. [4,5] Pseudoaneurysms occurring consequent to blunt carotid injury commonly affect branches of the ECA than the main ECA itself. [6] The clinical significance of the ECA and its branches is further reinforced by their application in a wide range of radiological and surgical procedures such as intra-arterial infusion chemotherapy [7,8] carotid stenting and endarterectomy [9,10] as well as various head and neck surgeries. [11-13]

A good knowledge of the normal anatomy and variations of ECA and its branches are of prime importance in both surgical and medical specialties. Both carotid endarterectomy and carotid stenting to

prevent recurrence of stroke warrant a thorough knowledge of the carotid system. [14] Extracranial-intracranial bypass procedure for revascularization uses the ECA or one of its branches as donor vessels. [15]

The aim of this study was to establish the relationship of External Carotid Artery with reference to Adjacent Anatomical landmarks in cadavers.

Material and Methods

The present prospective study was done in the Department of Anatomy, Netaji Subhas medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India. 60 hemi-necks obtained from 30 formalin embalmed cadavers (20 male and 10 female) were dissected and the external carotid arteries were traced from the origin to termination. Cadavers in which embalming had been done through CCA and those with injuries in the head and neck region were excluded from this study.

The cadavers were aged between 50 and 80 years. Variations encountered in the origin and branching pattern of the ECA were documented with digital photography. The data was tabulated and the percentage of cadavers with variations in the branching pattern of ECA as well as variations in the level of the carotid bifurcation were computed and analysed.

Results

Table 1: Variations in the level of bifurcation of common carotid artery

Level of origin	No. (%)	Laterality	
		Unilateral	Bilateral
Normal	60 (66.66%)	0	40
High (2a)	10 (16.66%)	0	10
High (2b)	8 (13.34%)	5	3
High (2c)	2 (3.34%)	2	0
Low	0	0	0

2a, between upper border of thyroid cartilage and greater cornua of hyoid bone; 2b, at the level of greater cornua of hyoid bone; 2c, above the level of greater cornua of hyoid bone

The ECA took origin at the level of upper border of thyroid cartilage (TC) in 40/60 cases (66.66%). Higher level of origin was noted in the remaining 20 of 60 cases (33.34%). Higher levels of carotid

bifurcation were further categorized keeping the TC as anatomical landmark. No lower levels of origin were noted in this study. The anteromedial position of

the ECA relative to the ICA at the level of the carotid bifurcation was noted in all the cases.

Table 2: Variations in the anterior branches of external carotid artery

Branching pattern	No. (%)
Separate origin	48 (80%)
Linguofacial trunk	10 (16.66%)
Thyrolinguofacial trunk	2 (3.34%)
Thyrolingual trunk	0

The anterior branches of the ECA include the STA, LA, and FA. Out of the 60 heminecks studied, separate origins for the anterior branches of the ECA were observed in 48 cases. In the remaining 12 cases, formation of common trunks was observed. The linguofacial trunk was the commonest observed variation with the

thyrolinguofacial trunk (TLFT) occurring only in a single case. The TLFT was found to arise 6 mm above the carotid bifurcation and after a short length of 3 mm, divided into the STA and a common linguofacial trunk. No thyrolingual trunks were observed.

Table 3: Distribution of accessory branches of external carotid artery

Name of accessory branch	No. (%) (n=60)
Superior laryngeal artery	4 (6.66)
Double ascending pharyngeal artery	2 (3.33)
Masseteric branch	1 (1.66)
Branch to Internal jugular vein	1 (1.66)

Accessory branches were found to arise from the ECA in 8 of 60 cases (13.33%).

Discussion

Surgeries like thyroidectomy, laryngectomy, faciomaxillary surgeries, tonsillectomy, glossectomy and other neck surgeries involve areas supplied by or related to branches of the ECA. [16] Orofacial reconstruction surgeries, including scalp transplantation, depend on the superior thyroid, lingual and facial arteries for their technical applicability, feasibility, and flap survival. [17]

The carotid bifurcation is an important anatomical and surgical landmark requiring special mention in the pathogenesis of carotid atheromatous disease and its consequent management by carotid stenting and endarterectomy. [18] According to Al-Rafiah et al. [19] and Mompeo and Bajo [20], the commonest

position of high carotid bifurcation was at the level of the hyoid bone in 25% and 36.85% cases respectively which correlates with our study. Lower levels of bifurcation have also been reported by the same authors with varying frequencies. Carotid bifurcations as low as intrathoracic bifurcations have also been reported in available literature. [21,22]

A low carotid bifurcation may be associated with Klippel-Feil anomaly [22] and may cause difficulties during surgeries like cervical discectomy. [23] With reference to previous similar studies, it may be noted that a higher level bifurcation is more common and lower bifurcations are less frequent. This correlates well with the present study also where no low level bifurcations were found. At the same time, a high carotid bifurcation (CB) should caution surgeons regarding the close proximity of

hypoglossal nerve and superior cervical ganglion as well as possible STA origin from the CB. [2] The position of the CB depends on how low or high ECA originates from the third aortic arch. [24]

It can thus be concluded that the level of the carotid bifurcation exhibits a great degree of anatomical variability and cautious ascertaining of its position is mandatory to avoid complications during angiographic and surgical interventions. The occurrence of common trunks in the branching pattern of the ECA has frequently been described in the current literature. The linguofacial trunk, by far, appears to be the commonest variation with high incidence as per literature reports. The linguofacial trunk was observed in 16.66% cases in the present study.

A unilateral TLFT was observed in a single case in our study (3.34%). This coincides with findings of previous studies where a TLFT is a relatively rare occurrence with the incidence reported to be 1.7% by Al-Rafiah et al. [19] According to Baik et al. [25], common linguofacial trunks arising from the ECA may place the LA or FA in closer proximity to the tonsillar fossa, increasing the risk of iatrogenic vessel injury. The linguofacial trunk is also a common site of traumatic pseudoaneurysm after tonsillectomy. [26]

Mata et al. suggests that the embryology of the combined trunks would be in keeping with the angiogenesis theory, which suggests that confluence of the vessels and vessels with large diameter are more common in fetuses compared with adults as TLFTs are more common in fetuses and tend to disappear in adults. [1] Hayashi et al. [27] observed the origin of APA from the ECA with relation to the origin of LA and found high origin above LA in 66% cases and below LA in 9% cases. We found a high origin of APA at the level of the LA in our study.

The branches of the ECA are the key landmarks for adequate exposure and appropriate placement of cross-clamps to carry out successful removal of plaque and minimize postoperative complications in a bloodless surgical field.²⁷ Caution must be paid with ligation of blood vessels of the carotid triangle, because if these blood vessels are not distinguished, this may have catastrophic consequences in cerebral circulation or it can cause bleeding in the region of the ECA. [28,29]

Conclusion

The anatomical knowledge of relationship of External Carotid Artery with reference to adjacent anatomical landmarks is helpful for vascular surgeons to plan surgeries and prevent complications during various diagnostic and therapeutic procedures. The branching pattern of the ECA in the neck shows considerable amount of variability and a clear anatomical understanding of the angioarchitecture will help to improve overall procedure outcome and prevent fatal complications. Prior angiographic assessment to ascertain the level of carotid bifurcation as well as the branching pattern of the carotid arterial system may prove valuable to avoid injury to vital structures such as hypoglossal nerve and minimize troublesome haemorrhage during surgical exploration of the head and neck region.

References

1. Mata JR, Mata FR, Souza MC, Nishijo H, Aversi Ferreira TA. Arrangement and prevalence of branches in the external carotid artery in humans. *Arrangement and Prevalence of Branches in the External Carotid Artery in Humans*. 2012;65-74.
2. Lo A, Oehley M, Bartlett A, Adams D, Blyth P, Al-Ali S. Anatomical variations of the common carotid artery bifurcation. *ANZ journal of surgery*. 2006 Nov;76(11):970-2.
3. Reid DB, Irshad K, Miller S, Reid AW, Reid W, Diethrich EB.

- Endovascular significance of the external carotid artery in the treatment of cerebrovascular insufficiency. *Journal of Endovascular Therapy*. 2004 Dec;11(6):727-33.
4. Heltzel S, Jelinek L, Jaynes D. Variation in the caudal branches of the external carotid artery: comparison of sex and side. *Med Res Arch* 2015; (1) :1-10.
 5. Devadas D, Pillay M, Sukumaran TT, Shrikantaiah VC, Basappa M, Hazrika S, Ravindranath R. Study of surgical anatomy of portal vein of liver segments by cast method and its clinical implications. *Anatomy & Cell Biology*. 2018 Dec;51(4):232-5.
 6. Nicoucar K, Popova N, Becker M, Dulguerov P. Pseudoaneurysm of the external carotid artery after a blunt facial trauma. *Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery*. 2008 Sep 1;65 (3) :E24-7.
 7. Ii N, Fuwa N, Toyomasu Y, Takada A, Nomura M, Kawamura T, Sakuma H, Nomoto Y. A novel external carotid arterial sheath system for intra-arterial infusion chemotherapy of head and neck cancer. *CardioVascular and Interventional Radiology*. 2017 Jul; 40 (7):1099-104.
 8. Tsurumaru D, Kuroiwa T, Yabuuchi H, Hirata H, Higaki Y, Tomita K. Efficacy of intra-arterial infusion chemotherapy for head and neck cancers using coaxial catheter technique: initial experience. *CardioVascular and Interventional Radiology*. 2007 Apr;30(2):207-11.
 9. Xu DS, Abruzzo TA, Albuquerque FC, Dabus G, Eskandari MK, Guterman LR, Hage ZA, Hurley MC, Hanel RA, Levy EI, Nichols CW. External carotid artery stenting to treat patients with symptomatic ipsilateral internal carotid artery occlusion: a multicenter case series. *Neurosurgery*. 2010 Aug 1;67(2):314-21.
 10. Al-Basheer M, Ferrar D, Nelson D, Vasudevan T. Outcome of the external carotid artery following carotid endarterectomy with added external carotid artery eversion endarterectomy. *Annals of Vascular Diseases*. 2011 Sep 25:1107270071-.
 11. Won SY. Anatomical considerations of the superior thyroid artery: its origins, variations, and position relative to the hyoid bone and thyroid cartilage. *Anatomy & cell biology*. 2016 Jun 1; 49(2):138-42.
 12. Banks ND, Hui-Chou HG, Tripathi S, Collins BJ, Stanwix MG, Nam AJ, Rodriguez ED. An anatomical study of external carotid artery vascular territories in face and midface flaps for transplantation. *Plastic and reconstructive surgery*. 2009 Jun 1;123 (6):1677-87.
 13. Shang JB, Li YH, Chen Y, He XG, Zeng QL, Wang JY. Clinical application of transarterial embolization for massive hemorrhage in the nasopharyngeal and maxillofacial regions. *Di 1 jun yi da xue xue bao*= Academic Journal of the First Medical College of PLA. 2004 Feb 1;24(2):210-2.
 14. Rajamani K, Chaturvedi S. Stroke prevention-surgical and interventional approaches to carotid stenosis. *Neurotherapeutics*. 2011 Jul;8(3):503-14.
 15. Germans MR, Regli L. Posterior auricular artery as an alternative donor vessel for extracranial-intracranial bypass surgery. *Acta neurochirurgica*. 2014 Nov;156(11):2095-101.
 16. Sanjeev IK, Anita H, Ashwini M, Mahesh U, Rairam GB. Branching pattern of external carotid artery in human cadavers. *J Clin Diag Res*, 2010;4: 3128-3133.
 17. Siemionow M, Kulahci Y. Facial transplantation. In *Seminars in plastic surgery*. Thieme Medical Publishers. 2007 Nov.; 21(04):259-268.
 18. Michalinos A, Chatzimarkos M, Arkadopoulos N, Safioleas M, Troupis T. Anatomical considerations on

- surgical anatomy of the carotid bifurcation. *Anatomy Research International*. 2016.
19. Al-Rafiah A, El-Haggagy AA, Aal IH, Zaki AI. Anatomical study of the carotid bifurcation and origin variations of the ascending pharyngeal and superior thyroid arteries. *Folia Morphologica*. 2011;70(1):47-55.
 20. Mompeó B, Bajo E. Carotid bifurcation: clinical relevance. *Eur J Anat*. 2015 Jan;19(1):37-42.
 21. Gomez CK, Arnuk OJ. Intrathoracic bifurcation of the right common carotid artery. *Case Reports*. 2013 Jan 9;2013: bcr2012007554.
 22. Gailloud P, Murphy KJ, Rigamonti D. Bilateral thoracic bifurcation of the common carotid artery associated with Klippel-Feil anomaly. *American journal of neuroradiology*. 2000 May 1;21(5):941-4.
 23. Gulsen S, Caner H, Altinors N. An anatomical variant: low-lying bifurcation of the common carotid artery, and its surgical implications in anterior cervical discectomy. *Journal of Korean Neurosurgical Society*. 2009 Jan;45(1):32.
 24. Kurkcuoglu A, Aytakin C, Oktem H, Pelin C. Morphological variation of carotid artery bifurcation level in digital angiography. *Folia Morphologica*. 2015;74(2):206-11.
 25. Baik FM, Chang AA, Green DA, Pakbaz RS, Bergeron CM. Post-tonsillectomy Lingual Artery Pseudoaneurysm. *The Laryngoscope*. 2011;121(S4 S4): S61-.
 26. Manzato L, Trivelato FP, Alvarenga AY, Rezende MT, Ulhôa AC. Endovascular treatment of a linguofacial trunk pseudoaneurysm after tonsillectomy. *Brazilian Journal of Otorhinolaryngology*. 2013; 79:524.
 27. Hayashi N, Hori E, Ohtani Y, Ohtani O, Kuwayama N, Endo S. Surgical anatomy of the cervical carotid artery for carotid endarterectomy. *Neurologia medico-chirurgica*. 2005;45(1):25-30.
 28. Delic J, Bajtarevic A, Isakovic E. Positional variations of the external and the internal carotid artery. *Acta Medica Saliniana*. 2009 Sep 17;39(2): 86-9.
 29. Bakhuraysah M. M., Alsalmi S. A., Alfadli S. N., Alotaibi S. A., Althomali D. S., Gharib A. F., Alrehaili A. A., & Alhuthali H. M. Assessing the knowledge and awareness of self-management among diabetic patients in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences*. 2022; 5(7): 2091–2104.